

Notes on the crab spider *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Linda Wiese², Karen Pagel³ & Jolandie Buck⁴

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda. dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA team member, Eastern Cape, Jeffrey's Bay, South Africa, lwiese9@gmail.com; ³Spider Club of Southern Africa. karentinroof@hotmail.com; ⁴Gondwana Private Game Reserve. gcf@gondwanagr.co.za

Abstract: The male of *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 was the first time recorded from Caffraria, South Africa. During surveys in the Eastern Cape, a female was the first time sampled with a male. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is described and photographs of live specimens provided and notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation are provided.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and numerous Thomisidae sampled. The second author (LW) sampled some strange thomisids from the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) that were eventually identified as *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883.

The genus *Phaenopoma*, an African endemic genus, is poorly known and presently known only from three species (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Members of *Phaenopoma* are characterised by their very flattened bodies, resembling members of the genus *Firmicus*, but the eye pattern and genitalia differ. Unfortunately the specimens lose their colour when placed in alcohol.

Phaenopoma nigropunctatum, the type species, is a South African endemic species that was described from a male by O. Pickard-Cambridge (1883) as *Nesis nigropunctatus*. The type locality was only listed as Caffraria, South Africa. The other two known species (*P. milloti* Roewer, 1961, from Senegal and *P. planum* Simon, 1895, from Sierra Leone) are based on immature specimens.

In the present paper we provide the first images of live specimens. The male is redescribed and the female described for the first time. New distribution records for the species are added, as well as notes of their behaviour and conservation status.

METHODS

For the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012), photographs of South African species were requested to obtain additional information on their morphology and distribution. The second author (LW) photographed the male and female in the Addo National Park, in the Eastern Cape and the third author (KP) provided photographs from Natures Valley in the Western Cape and the fourth author (JB) provided photos from Gondwana Private Nature Reserve.

Voucher specimens sampled during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Phaenopoma nigropunctatum (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883)

Nesis nigropunctatus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883: 361.

Phaenopoma nigropunctata Simon, 1895: 983; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b: 34.

Figures 1–2. *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum*. 1. Male from Addo National Park, dorsal view. 2. Female from Addo National Park, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–2. Linda Wiese.

Diagnostic characteristics: Male: (Figs 1 & 3–6). Size: TL 3–4 mm. Carapace, abdomen, and legs reddish brown in live specimens (colour fades in alcohol); abdomen ventrally a paler duller brown (Fig. 13); carapace with narrow dark marginal band (Fig. 3); palp dark; abdomen lateral border decorated with a row of small black spots (Figs 1, 3, 14, 15). Carapace as long as wide; truncated in front, constricted laterally at the margins; upper surface flat and level; eyes small and slightly different in size, occupying the whole width of carapace (Figs 6–7); both eye rows recurved, four median eyes smallest; anterior lateral eyes larger than posterior lateral eyes; lateral eyes situated on small tubercles; maxillae long, enlarged at the extremities, where they are obliquely and slightly roundly truncated on the outer side; labium more than half the length of the maxillae, constricted laterally near the middle; sternum oval, truncated anteriorly and pointed posteriorly (Fig. 13). Abdomen oblong, truncated anteriorly, and pointed posteriorly; very flat (Figs 11–12); sometimes abdomen posterior tip with short dark lines. Legs: front legs darker than carapace; first and second pairs longest; armed with a few paired slender spines beneath the tibiae and metatarsi of the first and second pair of legs; tarsal claws with small claw-tuft. Palpi large, dark brown with a strong retrotibial apophysis, with apex pointed and tip slightly twisted; cymbium with swollen lateral area; embolus medium length curved once around tegulum (Figs 8–9).

Females (Fig. 2) resemble males in general shape and size but are less flattened. In live specimen carapace and legs bright green with chelicerae and palpi pale brown. Abdomen fawn; dorsally decorated with 10–12 small black spots on lateral border and five pairs of green spots varying in size mediolaterally. Epigyne: atrium with U-shaped border (Fig. 10).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.88, 26.45), 1m, 1f (NCA 2011/1282); Alexandria State Forest (-33.705, 26.368), 1m (NCA 99/366); Paterson (-33.440, 25.968, 2m, 6 imm (NCA 2007/2078); The Haven, Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.240, 28.911), 3m, 1 imm (NCA 2007/329); East London (-33.01, 27.90), 1m (NCA 77/1089); Gonubie Beach (-32.933, 28.0167), 1m (NCA 77/1213); Grahamstown (-33.306, 26.525), 1m (NCA 88/498); Hogsback, Amatola Mts. (-32.594, 26.944), 1m (NCA 2014/466), same locality data, 1m (NCA 2014/493); Kei Mouth (-32.687, 28.374), 1m (NCA 2004/304); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89), 2f (NCA 88/495); Sundays River Valley (-33.39, 25.43), 1m (2007/2078); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.981, 23.559), 1 imm (NCA 79/84, 86/37). **KwaZulu-Natal:** 1.5 km E of Mtunzini Umlazi Nature Reserve (-29.95, 30.86), 1m (Natal Museum 12328); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-27.00, 32.83), 1m (NCA 2000/437). **Western Cape:** Natures Valley (-33.97, 23.57), 1m (photo); Gondwana Nature Reserve (-34.18, 22.12) (photo).

LIFESTYLE

They are free-living plant-dwellers. The males were very agile and moved around on the vegetation (Figs 13–15). Most of the specimens were sampled mainly by hand and sweep netting from vegetation in the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket, and Savanna biomes.

Figures 3–12. *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum*. 3–4. Male from Addo National Park (in alcohol). 5. Line drawing of male. 6–7. Eye pattern. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. 11–12. Male. Photo credits: 5, 6, 9. After O. Pickard-Cambridge (1883). 11–12. Karen Pagel. 3, 4, 7, 8, 10. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

13

14

15

Figures 13–15. *Phaeopoma nigropunctatum* male observed in low vegetation at the Gondwana Private Game Reserve. Photo credits: Jolandie Buck.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R. LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13: 121–127.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2020a. A list of spider species found in the Addo Elephant National Park, Eastern Cape province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1), a1578. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v62i1.1578>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020b. *The Thomisidae of South Africa*. Part 2 My-R. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 67 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7513276
- PICKARD-CAMBRIDGE O. 1883. On some new genera and species of spiders. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 51(3): 352–365.
- SIMON E. 1895. Histoire naturelle des araignées. *Paris* 1: 761–1084.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on May 2023 doi: 10.24436/2.

CONSERVATION

The species is mainly known from the Eastern Cape, with a few records from the Western Cape and KwaZulu-Natal. The species is protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020), Gondwana Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Buck 2023), Alexander State Forest, Cwebe Nature Reserve, Tsitsikamma National Park, and Umlazi Nature Reserve. Due to wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

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